

Veneers or Braces for Perfect Smile

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Abstract:- Modern dentistry materials and techniques are trending toward durable, effective, superior, and fast results. Veneers are cosmetic dentistry procedure whereas braces are the basis of orthodontic treatment. Orthodontic treatment or dental braces use for straightening teeth, while veneers can alter the shape, size, and shade of teeth. Both treatments play different roles in restoring the appearance of the smile. The main issue is that patients want quick results in short time in complex cases.

Keywords:- Veneers, Braces, Smile, Aesthetic.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, smile plays significant role in social life. Dental braces come in a wide variety of shape and styles, allowing patients to create ideal appearance. Braces used to shift and move teeth. They realign the teeth to their proper positions. They are non-invasive solution straighten your smile and improve your general health by correcting malocclusion which can cause headaches, inflammation of jaw joint and neck pain. If you are suffering from overbite, rapid maxillary expansion is the treatment option this procedure must be done when you are young in order to reposition your jaw into the ideal position so you can obtain veneers more easily. In relation to orthodontic treatment, changes in tooth color are likely caused by modifying the surface and structural properties. Additionally, the enamel morphology and texture are often altered by existing bracket debonding and adhesive removal techniques. which cannot be corrected with the use of polishing.

The optical characteristics of enamel surfaces may be impacted by these irreversible alterations. When orthodontic brackets are removed, there may occasionally be enamel surface fractures that act as stagnation zones for the growth of caries or discoloration.

Jaw alignment is the key to successful veneer placement whether you have an overbite or underbite. Veneers are an ideal option for people who want to fix gaps between their teeth as well as those who have discolored or irregularly shaped teeth. The stunning natural-looking smile that veneers may provide will certainly increase your self-confidence. You won't have to be concerned about your new smile losing its luster over time because they are incredibly stain-resistant. If your teeth are crowded, veneers will need to be thick and bulky. Many patients demand prompt outcomes. One major advantage of using veneers is that you can have a beautiful smile in a short amount of time.

In order to achieve success with veneers, proper timing of the procedures is just as crucial as choosing the best orthodontic solution. Dentists may advise patients to postpone veneer application until after orthodontic therapy is complete. This could make both treatments more effective while also preserving their integrity. There are some less invasive veneer techniques, including as minimal-preparation or no-preparation veneers. This makes it possible for a more seamless blending of therapies.

The dentist has to inform the patient of their midline position before treatment begins to promote patient satisfaction, even when correction with veneers might not be possible. Restorations can improve the midline appearance, however the gingival tissue may not adapt to major modifications.

II. CASE DESCRIPTION

34-year-old patient attended at the department of prosthodontics of dental clinic. He was complaining about the polydiastema. He declined orthodontic therapy, therefore veneers were the procedure.

Fig 1 Intra-Oral Frontal View

Fig 2 butt joint preparation

Fig 3 Digital Impression

Fig 4 Etching

Fig 5 Ultrasound

- Figure 1: intra-oral frontal view , patient with polydiastema
- Figure 2: butt joint preparation was applied to the teeth.
- Figure 3: intraoral scanner was used to directly create digital impression
- Figure 4: 4.5% hydrofluoric acid x 20 sec
- Figure 5: Distilled water 3 min4

Fig 6 Silane then Drying with air x 1 min

Fig 7 Veneers installed, final smile

III. DISCUSSION

20% of people don't smile for pictures on social media because they feel their teeth are unattractive. 81% of people believe that their teeth look unattractive in photographs. 42% of people said their smile was the first thing they would change about themselves .

Studies indicate that the mouth and smile are the most apparent facial features, making aesthetic dentistry one among the most effective tools for rejuvenating face features. Smile is your guide to esthetic dental treatment.

➤ *Conditions in which a Dental Veneer may be the most Appropriate Option*

- Stained or discolored teeth
- Teeth that are too small
- Fractured teeth
- multiple diastema
- malposed teeth not requiring orthodontic

➤ *Condition in which Braces may be the most Appropriate Option:*

- Teeth that don't close over each other probably when your mouth at rest
- Exist space for better prosthodontics replacement
- Sever crowded teeth
- Stress or fatigue on your jawline after chewing food
- Difficulty pronouncing certain sounds due to your tongue's position

If teeth appear to be proper on a clinical or radiological evaluation, it is preferable to restore old fillings on vital teeth that need prosthetic because after the veneers are finished, these fillings may result in pulpitis, which patient may think was caused by the prosthetic procedure.

The degree of misalignment will determine which dental procedure is ideal for you. In circumstances where the issue is minor or if the person just wants a cosmetic modification, veneers may be a better option than braces

When there is a moderate to severe structural issue, braces or Invisalign may be a better option.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A never-ending medical specialty is aesthetics. People will constantly look for the "ideal" image. Your dental objectives, desires, and concerns should be discussed with a skilled dentist. Orthodontists and cosmetic dentists can design a dental plan just for you. Orthodontics can be used at any age. In general, between the ages of 9 and 14 is the perfect age for braces. Although it can take a bit longer, adult braces are just as effective in achieving the desired outcomes. To prevent your teeth from moving back to their pre-treatment positions when treatment is complete, you'll need to wear a retainer.

Anyone wishing to improve their smile may consider dental veneers as a great option. They offer long-lasting effects in addition to being a quick and painless approach for fixing a number of cosmetic difficulties. Given the diversities of varieties and shapes available, it is easy to see why so many individuals choose it.

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